

The Importance Of Local Factors In Visual Identity Design

Görsel Kimlik Tasarımında Yerel Unsurların Önemi

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Abstract

Today, cities have historical, geographical, architectural, social-cultural values, etc. Some local features and differences create some advantages, differentiating towns from each other in terms of awareness. This situation creates urban memory and recognition; It highlights the concept of visual identity and branding. Visual identity is a discipline that involves the design and use of visual elements that a brand or organization uses to create a unique and recognizable look and feel. Visual identity design can include many elements, from the brand's logo to the color palette, typography, packaging design, and advertising materials. Local elements and geographically indicated products are essential in the branding process. Local elements are unique and defining elements that a brand or organization can use in its visual identity for a specific geographical region or cultural community. Local elements can help the brand create a stronger connection and better communication with its target audience in that region and increase their emotional commitment. In addition to the historical, cultural, and natural beauties of the cities, local characteristics such as symbols, colors, inhabitants, products, and tastes are the elements that differentiate towns from each other and gain identity. Identity can be defined as a concept expressed by documents, cards, numbers, or other identifiers containing identifiable characteristics and information that indicate a person's or object's uniqueness. Urban identity can be expressed as creating a memory of our city by giving human meaning to the features and visual elements that distinguish one town from another. This study aims to reveal the importance of local features in creating cities' visual identities and examine the impact of these features. The survey model, one of the qualitative research methods, was used. In line with the information obtained, suggestions have been developed to increase awareness regarding visual emphasis and design approach to local factors in creating visual identities of cities.

Key Words: Design, Brand, Institutional Identity, Local Identity.

Genişletilmiş Özet

Günümüzde kentlerin sahip oldukları; tarihi, coğrafi, mimari, sosyal-kültürel değerler vb. kimi yerel özellik ve farklılıklar, birtakım avantajlar yaratmakta ve bu da bilinirlik açısından şehirleri birbirlerinden ayırmaktadır. Kent hafızasının oluşturulmasında ve tanınırlık anlamında bu durum; görsel kimlik ve markalaşma kavramını ön plana çıkarmaktadır. Markalaşma sürecinde ise yerel unsurlar ile coğrafi işaretli ürünler önemli rol oynamaktadır. Kentlerin tarihi, kültürel ve doğal güzelliklerinin yanı sıra sembolleri, renkleri, yaşayanları, ürünleri, lezzetleri gibi yerel özellikleri de şehirlerin birbirlerinden ayrılma ve kimlik kazanma unsurlarıdır. Kimlik, bir kişinin veya nesnenin benzersizliğini gösteren, tanımlanabilir özelliklerini ve bilgilerini içeren belge, kart, numara veya diğer tanıtıcılarla ifade edilen bir kavram olarak tanımlanabilir. Kent kimliği de bir kenti diğerinden ayıran özellikleri ve görsel unsurlarını insani bir anlamlandırma ile yaşanan şehre dair bir bellek oluşturulması eylemi-süreci-faaliyetleri şeklinde ifade edilebilir. Bu çalışmanın amacı kentlerin görsel kimliklerinin oluşturulması sürecinde yerel özelliklerinin önemini ortaya koymak ve bu özelliklerin etkisini incelemektir. Çalışmada nitel araştırma tekniklerinden betimsel analiz tekniği kullanılmıştır. Ortaya çıkan bilgiler doğrultusunda, kentlerin görsel kimlik oluşturma sürecinde yerel etkenlere yönelik görsel vurgulama ve tasarım yaklaşımı bakımından bilinci artıracak öneriler geliştirilmiştir. Kimlikler, birçok farklı amaç için kullanılabilir. Yaygın olarak; eğitimde, adres kayıtlarında, seyahat ederken, banka işlemleri yaparken, oy kullanırken ve daha birçok durumda vatandaşlık özelliklerinin doğrulanmasında ve kimliğin kanıtlanmasında kullanılır. Günümüzde şehirler; kurum kimliği oluşturma ve markalaşma anlamında iletişim ve tanıtım organizasyonlarına yer vermektedir. Şehre ait dinamikler, başta o şehirde yaşayan bireyler olmak üzere tüm paydaşları temsil ettiğinden öncelikle onlarla bağ kurmalı ve kabul görmelidir. Kente ait tüm unsurlar bu anlamda ele alınması gereken görsel hafızayı ve tasarım potansiyelini oluşturmaktadır. Tasarımda yerel özelliklerin kullanımı görsel kimlik oluşturulmasında ön

plana çıkan bir yaklaşım biçimidir. Tarihsel süreç, mimari yapılar ve anıtlar, doğa ve coğrafya, toplumsal özellikler, folklorik, sanatsal ve kültürel miras, semboller, renkler, ekonomik değerler vb. yerel unsurlar, tasarımda kullanılarak, görsel hafıza oluşturulmasında dikkat çekebilmektedir. Görsel kimlik genellikle şu unsurları içerir: Logo: Bir organizasyonun veya markanın en tanınmış sembollerinden biri olan logo, görsel kimliğin temel taşıdır. Logo, genellikle bir kuruluşun veya markanın kimliğini temsil eden sembolik bir tasarımdır. Yerel perspektifinden bakıldığında Valilik, Kaymakamlık, Belediye, gelenekselleşmiş tanıtım etkinlikleri ve festivaller, üniversiteler vb. birçok kamu kurum ve kuruluşları, sahip oldukları logo ile tanınırlık kazanarak hedef kitlelerine ulaşırlar. Bu anlamda temsil ettikleri konu ve bölgeye ait semboller barındıran çalışmalar bilgilendirme ve fark edilirlilik anlamında öne çıkmaktadır. Renk Paleti: Belirli renklerin kullanımını ve kombinasyonlarını içerir. Renkler markanın hissini ve kişiliğini yansıtmak için seçilir. Renk unsuru hedef kitleyi ilk uyaran ve tasarıma yönlendiren, konuya dâhil eden, etkileşime sokan ve bağ kurmaya yarayan özelliktir. Kent kimliği oluşum sürecinde renk kullanımı, temsil ertme noktasında dikkat edilmesi gereken bir husustur. Tipografi: Belirli yazı karakterlerinin ve fontlarının kullanımını düzenler. Tipografi, markanın yazılı iletişimini biçimlendirir. Görsel simgelerle bütünleşen tipografiler dikkat çekme açısından daha etkili olabilmektedir. Kurumsal Kimlik Belgeleri: Kartvizitler, mektup kâğıtları, ambalajlar, broşürler ve diğer belgelerdeki tasarım kurallarını içerir. Yerel bağlamda tanıtıcı tüm materyaller bu başlıkta değerlendirilmektedir. Ek olarak etkinliklerde kullanılabilir tanıtım stratejisi ile uyumlu promosyon malzemeleri de (flama, bayrak, çanta, tişört, şapka vb.) üretilebilir. Web Sitesi Tasarımı: Bir markanın web sitesi, görsel kimliği çevrimiçi platformda temsil eder. Web sitesi tasarımı, internet üzerindeki içeriği ve kullanıcı deneyimini düzenlemek için yapılmaktadır. Bir web sitesinin tasarımı, kullanıcıların sitenin içeriğini kolayca bulmalarını, etkileşime girmelerini ve bilgiyi kolayca tüketmelerini sağlamak için düşünülmelidir. Web sitesinin kullanıcı dostu olması ve ziyaretçilerin istedikleri bilgilere hızlıca ulaşmalarını sağlamak için UX (kullanıcı deneyimi) tasarımı önemlidir. Farklı cihazlarda (bilgisayarlar, tabletler, akıllı telefonlar) tutarlı bir şekilde görüntülenmelidir. Web sitesindeki içerik düzenli ve erişilebilir olmalıdır. Web sitesi tasarımı sırasında güvenlik önlemleri de göz önünde bulundurulmalıdır. Renk Seçiminde Tarihi Vurgu: Markanın geleneksel veya geçmişe dayalı kimliğini yansıtan, tarihsel olarak önemli olan belirli renkler veya renk paletleri kullanımı, markanın sektördeki duruşunu ve kurumsal söylemini daha zengin hale getirebilir. Bireysel olduğu kadar kurumlar içinde önemli olan renkler markalaşma sürecinin etkili öğelerindedir. Hikâye anlatımı: Markanın tarihini, kuruluşunu veya gelişimini anlatan hikâyeler, web sitesi, reklam kampanyaları veya diğer iletişim araçları aracılığıyla paylaşılmaktadır. Markanın tarihindeki önemli dönüm noktaları veya kuruluş yıldönümleri, özel etkinlikler veya kampanyalar düzenleyerek vurgulanmaktadır. Markanın tarihsel öğeleri doğru bir şekilde temsil etmesi ve hedef kitle ile etkili bir şekilde iletişim kurması için tasarım ve iletişim açısından dikkatli olmak gerekir. Yerel öğeler; kültür, gelenek, çevre ve toplumun ihtiyaçları, işletmenin bulunduğu coğrafi bölge ile olan ilişkisini yansıtır. İşletmeler, yerel öğeleri iş stratejilerine dâhil ederek, yerel toplumla daha yakın ilişki kurar, işletmelerin topluluklarına daha iyi hizmet vermesini ve yerel müşterileri bağımlılığı oluşturmasını sağlar. Görsel kimlik, markanın veya organizasyonun yerel öğeleri, yerel kültür ve coğrafya ile bağlantılı özel öğeleri temsil etmek için kullanılır. Bu, markanın yerel topluluklara daha yakın hissetmesini ve yerel pazarlarda daha iyi bir uyum sağlar. Görsel kimlik oluşturma da yerel öğelerin kullanımı hakkında bilinmesi gereken bazı noktalar bulunmaktadır. Her şehrin kendine özgü bir kimliği ve bu kimlikten beslenen tanıtım unsurları vardır. Şehrin fiziki, beşeri ve coğrafi konumu, sembol olarak karşılık bulabilmektedir. Coğrafi bölge sembollerini veya doğal özelliklerini yansıtan renkler marka kimliği içinde kullanılabilir. Şehrin sanayi ve tarımsal üretimi, yeryüzü şekilleri, iklimi, yerel kimlik oluşturmada iletişim ve pazarlama anlamında önemli rol oynar ve bu çalışmada yer verilen örneklerde de görüleceği üzere tanıtım unsuru olan logolarda karakterize edilerek göz önüne serilmiştir. Yerel öğeler, markanın yerel topluluklarla daha fazla bağlantı kurmasına ve yerel pazarlarda daha iyi bir kabul görmesine yardımcı olabilir. Ancak, bu tür öğeleri kullanırken kültürel ve yerel duyarlılığa saygı göstermek çok önemlidir. Yerel semboller veya motifler, marka için anlamlı ve saygılı bir şekilde kullanılmalıdır. İşletmeler için başarı, görsel kimlik ve yerel öğelerin başarılı bir şekilde birleştirilmesini gerektirir. Görsel kimlik, işletmenin logosu ve tasarımıyla yerel öğeleri içeren yerel motifler veya sembollerle birleştirilebilir. Bu, işletmenin topluluğuna aidiyet hissini artırabilir. Ayrıca, işletmeler, yerel etkinliklere katılarak, yerel sivil toplum kuruluşlarına destek vererek veya yerel tedarikçilerle iş yaparak yerel öğeleri güçlendirebilirler. Bu, işletmenin toplumla daha yakın bir ilişki kurmasına ve yerel değerlere saygı duymasına yardımcı olabilir. Sonuç olarak, görsel kimlik ve yerel öğeler, işletmeler için büyük önem taşıyan iki temel bileşendir. İyi bir görsel kimlik, işletmenin dış dünyadaki imajını güçlendirirken, yerel öğeler ise işletmenin toplumla olan bağını destekler. Bu iki faktörün başarılı bir şekilde birleştirilmesi, işletmelerin yerel topluluklara daha iyi hizmet vermesini ve müşteri bağlılığını artırmasını sağlar.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Tasarım, Marka, Kurumsal Kimlik, Kent Kimliği.*

Introduction

Identity is a document or card containing information such as a person's name, photograph, date of birth, gender, nationality, social security number, etc. and is usually issued by government agencies. Identities can be used for many different purposes. Generally, It is used to verify citizenship characteristics and prove identity in education, address registration, traveling, banking transactions, voting, many other situations. Additionally, identity is a means by which people introduce themselves to others and participate in social relations. It helps a person express the culture, community, or belief they feel they belong to and express this identity to others.

People have unique personalities through which they introduce themselves to those around them and become known. Individuals behave by their selves and differ from others; They are often

evaluated based on their identity. As economic, social, political pressures increase worldwide, the addresses and functions of institutions and organizations change frequently. These changes require organizations to adapt their identities. Advances in technology, expansion of trade, and the rapid introduction of manufactured products or services to world markets necessitate the evolution of institutions. Every business, regardless of its product or service, has a managerial, strategic or supporting function regarding decision-making mechanisms (Sampson, 1995, p.26). Therefore, the concept of identity is of great importance. At this point, it is possible to divide the issue of identity into three main groups: individual identity, collective identity, and corporate identity.

Individual Identity; It is the set of features that distinguish each individual from others and make them unique. These features are personal and ask, "Who am I?" It constitutes the answer to the question.

Social Identity; It is a type of identity that reveals the difference of certain groups from others and reflects a generally experienced process. It expresses the identity of groups that have existed over time and are recognized in a particular area.

Corporate identity; It is not limited to visual elements such as the organization's logo, colors and, emblem. Corporate identity is a broader concept that includes an organization's mission, values, way of doing business, and relationship style. Corporate identity includes elements such as corporate behavior, corporate communication, and philosophy, and corporate design, which includes visual elements (Bozkurt, 2004, p.111).

Method

The research examines the role of local elements, usage areas and graphic design principles in creating corporate identity. Covering local stories with a well-designed logo and website is a must in the context of brand and corporate identity. The article emphasizes how critical local features are in creating the visual identities of cities. The survey model, one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the research. The survey model allows the quantitative identification of trends, attitudes or opinions in the universe through studies conducted on a sample selected from a universe. With scanning studies, it is tried to reveal what the phenomenon is as fully and accessible as possible (Sönmez & Alacapınar, 2011, p.46-47). In addition, visual documents were meticulously examined, classified and evaluated. These analyzes provide important information about how the visual identities of cities can be shaped.

Corporate Identity and Corporate Culture: The Cornerstones of Businesses

Just as identity distinguishes individuals from each other, it also distinguishes institutions from other institutions (Akıncı Vural & Erkan, 2018, p.13). The key to success for any business is creating and maintaining an excellent corporate identity and a solid corporate culture. These two concepts reflect the identity and values of a company, creating a sense of unity and commitment among employees.

What is Corporate Identity?

According to Olins (1990, p.11), corporate identity is an indicator that indicates 'who an institution is', 'what it does', and 'how it does it' and constitutes a structure that includes the institution's products and services, internal and external environment, communication style and behaviour. Corporate identity is the face of a business that it presents to the outside world. This face includes visual elements such as the company's logo, colors, slogans, and general appearance. However, corporate identity is not just visual; It should also reflect the core values and mission of the business. A business's identity provides customers and potential customers with an understanding of what the company is, what it does, and why it is essential.

Corporate identity and brand concepts feed on each other and need to be taught and executed together (Ergene & Ernek Alan, 2022, p.16).

A brand is a familiar name, symbol, logo, color, or other identifying feature associated with a company's products or services. A brand represents an identity that helps consumers distinguish a

product or service from others. Brands often promise trust and quality to customers and have unique features that distinguish a company's products and services from competitors.

What are the Basic Elements of the Brand?

Name. One of the most essential elements of the brand is its name. A good brand name should be permanent in consumers' memory and be associated with the product or service. Logos, in which the brand's name or initials are usually stylized, clearly communicate the brand's name and are effective in strengthening the brand identity. These can create a unique look using colour, font and style to reflect the perceived value and character of the brand. Logos often increase brand awareness due to their simplicity and familiarity.

For example, the Kodak logo is the logo of a brand that is known worldwide and has a long history. Kodak is known for its long-standing presence in the camera and film industry. The Kodak logo has changed several times since the company's founding, but the most recognizable and iconic is the "Kodak" logo, which is a stylized version of the word "Kodak" in yellow and red.

This logo clearly displays the brand's name, and the circular pattern next to the letter "K" evokes a lens or roll of photographic film. The choice of colors is vibrant and eye-catching, giving a feeling of warmth, energy and enthusiasm.

Visual 1. Logo examples

Logo and Visual Identifiers. Brands often create a visual identity using a special logo or specific colors and designs. This helps consumers visually recognize the brand. For example, Coca-Cola's logo represents the brand's name in a unique font and red color, and has become a globally recognized symbol.

Another example, Amazon is an iconic design that represents the globally recognized and successful e-commerce platform. Amazon's logo has a simple and impressive design that reflects the name and character of the company.

The Amazon logo includes the text "Amazon" with an arrow below the brand's name. This arrow starts from the letter "A" and extends to the letter "Z". This design reflects Amazon's claim to offer its customers everything "from A to Z". At the same time, the inscription "Amazon" located under the arrow emphasizes the reliability and easy recognition of the brand.

As for color selection, black is usually used, but color variations such as white or blue can also be used to adapt the logo to different backgrounds or applications. The Amazon logo has a simple and clean design, which reflects the reliability and professionalism of the brand. This logo represents Amazon's customer-centric service approach and wide product range.

Visual 2. Logo examples

Slogan. A brand is often associated with a specific saying or phrase. This slogan summarizes the brand's core values, mission, or product. For example, Nike's famous slogan "Just Do It" was first used in an advertising campaign in 1988. This slogan is used as an encouraging phrase to overcome any challenge encountered while playing sports or in life. Apple's most well-known and iconic slogan is "Think Different". This slogan was used in Apple's advertising campaign between 1997 and 2002. The slogan is designed to highlight Apple's approach to diversity and creativity. This campaign had a huge impact as part of the return of Steve Jobs and Apple's revival.

Visual 3. Logo and slogan examples

Customer Experience. The brand creates a consumer experience about the product or service offered. Customer satisfaction is an essential factor in building brand loyalty.

Product and Service Quality: A brand is often associated with quality products or services. Customers identify the brand with this standard of quality.

Brand Value. How valuable a brand is in the market depends on customer loyalty, brand awareness, and other factors.

Branding can help a company establish a competitive advantage and offer consumers a sense of reliability and consistency. A strong brand be the first choice that comes to consumers' minds when they think of a particular product or service. Therefore, companies often pay great attention to brand strategies and management.

What is Corporate Culture?

Culture is a phenomenon created by humans and a human life requirement (Tezcan, 1993, p. 13). It refers to the learned aspect of human behavior. When a special culture is mentioned, the common lifestyle of the people in that society is understood (Emiroğlu, 2000, p. 2).

Ralph Linton's (1945, p. 32) definition is as follows: A culture is a combination of learned behaviors and the consequences of these behaviors. The elements that makeup culture are shared and transmitted by members of a particular society. Corporate culture forms the basis of the internal functioning of a business. This includes the business relationships among employees, leadership style, work ethics, values, and the overall atmosphere of the workplace. Corporate culture tells a business's employees who they are, why they are here, and how they should do their jobs. An excellent corporate culture encourages employees to be committed to their jobs and embrace the business's goals.

The Relationship between Corporate Identity and Corporate Culture

It may be challenging to give a clear definition of the concept of culture, but when culture is mentioned today, concepts such as 'cultured person'; 'cultural interests'; and 'intellectual purposes related to humanity' usually come to mind (Yenici, 2019, p. 21). Corporate identity and corporate culture are elements that complement each other. A business's corporate identity helps communicate its values and goals to employees and the outside world as part of its corporate culture. At the same time, corporate culture reflects the business's corporate identity, creating employees' commitment to their jobs and a positive atmosphere in the workplace. According to Williams (1993, p.11), culture "today encompasses all areas from language to journalism, fashion, and advertising, not only expressing traditional arts and forms of intellectual production but also including art and philosophy."

Successful businesses combine corporate identity and corporate culture harmoniously. This allows the company to convey a consistent message externally and internally. A good corporate identity and culture are the cornerstones of the business's sustainable success.

As a result, corporate identity and corporate culture are critical for every business. While an excellent corporate identity determines how the company appears in the outside world, a solid corporate culture shapes the internal functioning of the company. These two factors define the business's identity and values, increase customer and employee loyalty, and lay the foundation for long-term success.

Visual Identity Concept and Creating a Visual Identity in the Perspective of Local Elements

There is a standard basic concept between the symbols used by nations from past to present and the symbols adopted by modern institutions after technological, social, and cultural evolution. Two of the most important of these basic concepts are "institution" and "identity" (Akgöz, 2020, p. 621).

Visual identity is one of the crucial factors that have an impact on the choices of the target audience, gaining a place in their minds and ensuring distinction (Haşiloğlu & Özpolat, 2019, p. 191). Visual identity includes the visual elements of a business, namely logo, color, typography, and design style. These elements are used in the business's promotional materials, website, advertisements and product packaging. An excellent visual identity has a common basic concept among the symbols adopted after cultural evolution. Two of the most important of these basic concepts are "institution" and "identity" (Akgöz, 2020, p. 621). It should reflect the identity and values of the business and leave a solid first impression on customers.

Visual identity is the set of design, color, typography, and symbols that a company, organization, brand, or individual uses to create a visually identifiable and distinguishable identity. Visual identity is often expressed through graphic design, such as logos, business cards, letter paper, websites, packaging and other visual communication tools. Graphic design is a discipline that uses visual elements that strengthen communication (Ünal Gerdan, 2023, p. 360). Visual identity combines

of graphic and verbal elements that create a system that defines and represents the brand (Clifton, 2004, p. 113).

Visual identity creates and promotes the first impression of an organization or brand. An inconsistent or unclear visual identity can cause communication problems with the target audience and weaken brand promotion. Therefore, creating and maintaining a visual identity is important to increase and strengthen a brand's recognizability.

Visual identity is also essential to ensure strong brand recognition and create emotional connections with consumers. A good visual identity can communicate a brand's quality, reliability and consistency.

Today, cities include communication and promotional organizations in terms of creating corporate identity and branding. Since the dynamics of the town represent all stakeholders, especially the individuals living in that city, they must first establish a bond with them and be accepted. All city elements constitute the visual memory and design potential that needs to be considered in this sense.

Using of local features in design is a prominent approach to creating visual identity. Historical process, architectural structures and monuments, nature and geography, social characteristics, folkloric, artistic and cultural heritage, symbols, colors, economic values, etc. Using local design elements, they can attract attention in creating visual memory.

Visual identity usually includes these elements:

Logo. One of the most familiar symbols of an organization or brand, the logo is the cornerstone of visual identity. A logo is a symbolic design that usually represents the identity of an organization or brand. It consists of graphic elements that reflect a business's name, slogan or core values. The purpose of the logo is to introduce the brand to the target audience, convey the values of the brand, and distinguish the brand from other brands. Logos are often used in various communication tools, such as websites, product packaging, advertisements, brochures, and other marketing materials.

From a local perspective, Governorship, District Governorate, Municipality, traditional promotional events and festivals, universities, etc. Many public institutions and organizations reach their target audiences by gaining recognition with their logos. In this sense, works containing symbols of the subject and region they represent stand out in terms of information and awareness.

In Visual 4, in 2003, Gaziantep Metropolitan Municipality designed a corporate logo to be among the global brand cities with its more livable, more touristic culture, history, gastronomy, fair, and congress tourism by placing 'people' at the center. The statements of Emrah Yücel (2016), the president of the I Mean It agency, which made the design the logo are as follows: The letter "G", like other letters in the Gaziantep font, is built on a grid structure consisting of hexagons and triangles. This structure is similar to the "Heavy Duty" structure used by the masters who make copper decorations in Gaziantep. The letter "G" was chosen because it has a carrier feature due to its structure. The "G" emblem is designed using wire for black and white applications and dimensional for 3D applications and is included in other pictograms to be used in different areas (<https://mediacat.com/gaziantep-markalasin/>).

Visual 4. Gaziantep city logo

Color Palette. Includes the use and combinations of specific colors. Colors are chosen to reflect the feel and personality of the brand. The color element is the first feature that stimulates the target audience and directs them to the design, involves them in the subject, engages them in interaction, and helps establish a bond. Color, which has significant effects on human psychology, is the subject of many studies ranging from appetite to behavior, emotion to marketing.

The use of color in the process of urban identity formation is an issue that needs to be consideration in terms of representation. Characteristics of the geography (sea, lake, river, mountain, etc.), economic values (agricultural industry production, products, etc.), natural structure, vegetation and endemic species, social structure, beliefs and traditions, etc. Color arrangements using the colors reflected by the elements can be an approach that can make a difference in the formation of local identity.

In Visual 5, three different geographical symbols in the logo of Gölcük Municipality (Kocaeli) are analyzed with colors. Geographical symbols symbolize the natural, industrial, and tourist features of Gölcük, which was founded during the republican period and has been highly developed until today.

Visual 5: Gölcük municipality logo

In Visual 6, the green and yellow used in the Harran University logo represent the Harran Plain and the agricultural activities, the blue color represents the water that gives life to the region, the motif represents the stone decorations in the ruins of the historical Harran University, and the structure in the middle means the Harran Tunnel.

Visual 6. Harran university logo

Typography. Regulates the use of specific typefaces and fonts. Typography shapes the brand's written communication. Typographies integrated with visual symbols can be more effective in attracting attention.

The logo of Ürgüp Municipality was designed by Lecturer Zafer Türkmen and his team with the "Three Beauties" form. A path is hidden between two aesthetic forms. This road is an invitation to Ürgüp. The original font used in the logo, transitional colors, flexible paths, and the 'Ü' within itself. It has the characteristics of a fairy tale land with its letter cycle and fairy chimney visuals. Scientifically, the logo is placed within the golden ratio.

Visual 7. Ürgüp municipality logo

Graphic Elements. Special graphics, patterns, or symbols can be part of the brand's visual identity. It attracts attention as a means of expression that introduces the city in terms of local features. Visual 8 shows the work done for Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality. The logo was designed by Metin Edremit. It started to be used due to a competition in 1969 and has remained an effective symbol until today. The logo symbolizes Istanbul's historical and architectural structure with its general structure. When it comes to Istanbul, the first thing that comes to mind is the slogan and image of "the city of seven hills" and the city's unique view, and the walls, minarets, and domes in its magnificent silhouettes are the first visual symbols that catch the eye. In this sense, The triangles in the center of the logo symbolize the seven hills of Istanbul, the city walls symbolize the Asian and European sides, the Bosphorus and the historical walls, and the minarets symbolize the mosques in Istanbul. In the logo, seven triangles represent each hill for Istanbul, defined as the Seven Hills. Some of these hills are Hagia Sophia and Sultanahmet Mosques and the hill where Topkapi Palace is located. Blue, used as the color, is not only the symbol of the sea that dominates the entire city but also the symbol of power and reliability from the Ottoman Empire to the present day.

Visual 8. İstanbul metropolitan municipality logo

Local symbols or patterns can show respect for local culture and make identity more familiar. For example, images of local motifs or craft patterns, local landscapes, people, or local products can be used to introduce and highlight local elements.

Visual 9. Municipality logos

While designing the logo of Aydın Metropolitan Municipality, shown in Visual 9, the figure of "Efe" one of the symbols of the liberation of the city and the nation, was used as the main theme. While creating the figure, the concepts of "fig and olive leaves", which are important sources of income for the city, were also used as visual elements.

In the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality logo, the pointed mountains symbolize Uludağ, the minarets on the sides symbolize the Ulu Mosque, the dome-shaped structure in the middle represents the Green Tomb, and the two people at the bottom of the logo represent the sword-shield team, which is a crucial folklore feature. The stars of the European Union flag inspire the twelve stars around them.

The city of Denizli has a deep history and is frequently identified with the rooster figure. This symbol carries the traces of the city's ancient past to the present and has an essential place in the municipality logo. Additionally, the symbol representing Pamukkale closely connects with the name Denizli. Pamukkale travertines were formed by hot water springs located in the central district of Denizli and formed by fractured structures on the calcareous ground. Although there are similar formations worldwide, Pamukkale's unique view and fascinating nature left an impressive impression on people and created an image identified with the city of Denizli (Uğur, 2020, p. 906).

Corporate Identity Documents.

Includes design rules for business cards, letter papers, packaging, brochures, and other documents.

All promotional materials in the local context are evaluated under this heading. Additionally, promotional materials (pennants, flags, bags, t-shirts, hats, etc.) that are compatible with the promotional strategy used at events can also be produced. Visual 10 contains the corporate identity visuals of Balıkesir province, which has implemented branding activities with the slogan "full of life". The city, which has a rich content with its economic values, especially history, tourism, nature, meat, dairy and seafood, olives, and olive oil, has been visualized with the "Brand City Balıkesir" concept.

Visual 10. Balıkesir brand city project

Website Design. A brand's website represents the visual identity of the online platform. Website design is done to organize the content and user experience on the internet. The design of a website should enable users to easily find, interact with, and consume information on the site's content. UX (user experience) design is essential to ensure the website is user-friendly and visitors can quickly access the information they want. It should be visually appealing, and the color scheme, font choice, images, and graphics should reflect the brand's or content's spirit. It should be displayed consistently across devices (computers, tablets, smartphones). The content on the website should be organized and accessible. Security measures should also be taken into consideration during website design. Website design is a constantly changing field that evolves with technological innovations, user habits, and market demands. Therefore, it is essential to adapt to current trends and technologies.

Visual 11. Web page banner

History. Another critical issue in creating a visual identity is history. The historical process and contents are essential to reflect the brand or organization's roots, history, and values. Historical elements can strengthen the brand's identity, connect with the past, and increase consumer trust.

Symbols referring to local values, history, and origins used in the branding process effectively emphasize the brand's traditional values and history. In this sense, the logo prepared for Erzincan Municipality (Özpolat, K., & Haşiloğlu, M. F. (2019) (Visual 12) is a good example. Additionally, the typography used alongside the logo has a modern and elegant design and a wide character set.

Visual 12. Erzincan municipality logo

The Anatolian Seljuk period is the origin of the double-headed eagle motif in the Erzincan Municipality logo, adopted in 1989. The figure of a double-headed eagle can be seen in many works of art from the period that have survived to the present day. The rams in the logo belong to the Akkoyunlu period when the Turkification and Islamization process of Eastern Anatolia ended. Due to the importance of Erzincan in the Akkoyunlu State, this detail was emphasized in the logo. In addition, the logo's copper, oil lamp, dome, sword, and minaret motifs reflect the city's history and culture. The grape figure on the eagle's tail symbolizes grape cultivation in the region. It represents the Üzümlü district, which takes its name from this economic value, and the "Cimin Grape", the world's first and only patented grape, with the application of Üzümlü Municipality to the Turkish Patent Institute in 2001. This logo is a design that covers the province of Erzincan and its values and reflects all aspects and cultural riches of the city in terms of local characteristics (<https://www.dogugazetesi.com/erzincan-logosu-uzerine>).

Historical Emphasis in Color Selection: Using historically significant colors or color palettes that reflect the brand's traditional or historical identity can enrich the brand's stance and corporate discourse in the industry. Colors, essential for institutions and individuals, are practical elements of the branding process. So much so that some color codes are associated with that brand; the meanings of some of the colors that significantly impact brand management can be explained as follows. Red prompts people to make quick decisions; it is the color of adventure, excitement, love, and energy. It is especially preferred by food and beverage brands. Although its effect on people varies depending on the tones it is used in, green is the color of sharing, harmony, balance, health, and money. It is the color preferred by the defense sector and brands with an environmentally friendly image. Often used together, black is the color of power and elegance, and white is the color of purity and peace. It is the choice of brands that want to create a straightforward personality.

Turkey's first domestic car, Togg, was inspired by the beauties of Turkey for the exterior colors of its first electric smart car, the C-SUV, launched in the first quarter of 2023. Togg named the exterior colors of the car, inspired by the fascinating beauties of Turkey, "Anadolu", "Gemlik", "Oltu", "Kula", "Cappadocia" and "Pamukkale".

Togg brings together the blue waters of Gemlik, where its campus is located, under the shade of olive trees, the red that reflects the friendliness and passion of the Anatolian lands, the eye-catching blackness, shiny texture and solid structure of the Oltu stone, and the millions of years of history of the earth with its natural structure, rocks, and valleys. The exterior colors of the C-SUV combine the gray magnificence of the C-SUV, the soil and sand beige of Cappadocia's extraordinary natural wonder fairy chimneys, and the dazzling whiteness of Pamukkale travertines.

Visual 13. Togg color scale

Historical Emphasis in Typography. Old typefaces or typography styles can be used to pay homage to the brand's history.

Visual 14. Coca-cola logo

The Coca-Cola logo dates back to 1886 when chemist John Stith Pemberton invented the drink. Logo (Visual 14) The general style, except for the handwriting style with two capital Cs, the movable font, and the color, has remained unchanged.

Storytelling. Stories telling the brand's history, foundation, or development are shared through the website, advertising campaigns, or other communication tools. In Visual 15, the web page of the Ülker brand shows where the brand has come from in the historical process on a product basis. Organizing special events or campaigns emphasizes significant milestones in the brand's history or anniversaries.

History is a powerful tool to emphasize the brand's character, stability, and reliability. However, when using historical elements, it is essential to integrate them meaningfully and respectfully. For the brand to accurately represent historical elements and communicate effectively with the target audience, it is necessary to be careful in terms of design and communication.

Visual 15. Ülker brand history

Conclusion and discussion

Understanding how to combine visual identity and local elements is essential for a business to be successful. While visual identity determines how the company is perceived in the outside world, local elements reflect the environmental context of the industry and its relationship with society.

Local items: Culture, tradition, environment, and society's needs reflect the relationship of the business with the geographical region in which it is located. By incorporating local elements into their business strategies, businesses engage more closely with the local community, enabling them to serve their communities better and build local customer loyalty.

Visual identity represents local elements of the brand or organization, specific elements linked to local culture and geography. This makes the brand feel closer to local communities and provides a better fit in local markets. There are some points to know about using local elements in creating a visual identity.

Each city has its own identity and promotional elements that feed on this identity. The city's physical, human, and geographical location can be expressed as a symbol. The brand identity can use geographical region symbols or colors reflecting natural features. The city's industrial and agricultural production, landforms, and climate play an essential role in creating a local identity in terms of communication and marketing. As can be seen in the examples included in this study, they are characterized and displayed in logos, which are promotional elements.

For example, 'green Bursa' shows that the natural and cultural beauties of Bursa City coincide with the color green. For Trabzon in the north of our country, 'burgundy-blue' is used; for Rize, tea production is the source of income of the region, and 'green' color is used in local elements because Konya is the grain warehouse of Turkey. These colors are also elements included in city graphics. For example, benches, paving stones, information signs and infographics, rail system colors, etc. used in parks and gardens. This strengthens local connections.

Local elements can help the brand connect more with local communities and gain market acceptance. However, respecting cultural and regional sensitivity when using such items is crucial. Local symbols or motifs should be used in a meaningful and respectful way to the brand.

The use of the brand in the local language and the font choice are also essential to respect local elements. Communication in the local language creates a better impact on local markets. The role of local elements in the brand identity is emphasized by introducing local elements by collaborating with local artists, handicraft producers, or cultural organizations and by telling stories focusing on the brand's origins and local connections.

Success for businesses requires the successful incorporation of visual identity and local elements. The visual identity can incorporate local motifs or symbols that integrate local elements in the business's logo and design. This can increase the business' sense of belonging to its community.

Additionally, businesses can leverage local elements by participating in local events, supporting local nonprofits, or doing business with local suppliers. This can help the company establish a closer relationship with the community and respect local values.

As a result, visual identity and local elements are two critical components of businesses. While an excellent visual identity strengthens the company's image in the outside world, local elements support the bond of the business with society. Successfully combining these two factors enables firms to serve local communities better and increase customer loyalty.

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Araştırmacıların Katkı Oranı Beyanı

Birinci Yazar %50, İkinci Yazar %50,

Çatışma Beyanı

Makalenin herhangi bir aşamasında maddi veya manevi çıkar sağlanmamıştır.

Yayın Etiği Beyanı

Bu makalenin planlanmasından, uygulanmasına, verilerin toplanmasından verilerin analizine kadar olan tüm süreçte "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında uyulması belirtilen tüm kurallara uyulmuştur. Yönergenin ikinci bölümü olan "Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiğine Aykırı Eylemler" başlığı altında belirtilen eylemlerden hiçbiri gerçekleştirilmemiştir. Bu araştırmanın yazım sürecinde bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamıştır. Bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir.